

DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS USING MOBILE DEVICES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7632612>

Abstract. *It is known that mobile phones as portable and accessible devices are being used for educational purposes, especially language education. The general aim of this study is to analyze innovative ways of promoting linguistic competencies of primary education school students through mobile- assisted language teaching and select appropriate technologies suitable to classroom of primary education in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *mobile assisted language learning, criteria, primary education, mobile applications.*

In the digital age, the young generation tends to spend a considerable amount of their time online. Responding to this general habit of young students, educators have begun using mobile devices such as tablets or smartphones for pedagogical purposes. As a result, this turned the perspectives of teachers about mobile technologies into ones of considering them as learning tools.

To build the theoretical background of this research, the study also conducted a systematic review of the literature on primary education and mobile-assisted language learning methodology. To begin with, studies on methodological and instructional practices of primary education [1-3] have been reviewed in general.

Instructional quality study in primary education [2] was also conducted, with the identification of patterns, predictors, and relations to student achievement and motivation, examined social well-being in primary education students. The study of contributed to promoting primary education students' social behavior.

Regarding the mobile-assisted language learning literature, mobile learning methodology based on games is proven to improve the students' linguistic competencies in an innovative manner. Most importantly, this innovative way of mobile language learning is increasingly satisfying the basic needs of primary education students as they tend to provide an engaging learning environment where the students play games full of immersive, voluntary, and enjoyable activities. Language learning through gameplay not only provides a fun but also enables children to find their meanings by making sense of the language system, contradicting the traditional educational approaches that make the students stay passive and their instructor becomes the conductor of content and actions. Some games define learning outcomes designed to balance subject matter with gameplay [4]. This kind of gameplay enables students to apply their conceptual knowledge. Game-based learning tasks very often come up with the use of mobile devices in classrooms and teachers are faced with the design of game-based learning activities by integrating suitable mobile applications. In this regard, the selection of pedagogically relevant mobile applications becomes the primary objective of designing an appropriate lesson plan. For this reason, this paper aims to determine mobile applications and feedback of teachers who teach language to primary education students by using those applications, based on the literature analysis of selecting the mobile technology meeting the needs of the language classroom.

This article determines various significant evaluation criteria for effective mobile

application selection in teaching language to primary education students. Similar studies have already explored the selection of mobile applications for mobile learning classrooms, but none of them has yet focused on mobile language learning of primary education students. This study tries to fill this research gap in mobile-assisted language learning literature and to provide an efficient framework for effective mobile application selection that can be used in the next levels of language education classrooms (such as higher education) as well.

Based on the practices of primary education and mobile-assisted language teaching methodology [1-3], we identified four main mobile applications that suit with pedagogical and physiological needs of primary education students (aged from 12 to 16) because of their game and pedagogical features. They are Kahoot, toontastic, wooclap.com, and wordwall. From them, only toontastic 3D application is an offline mobile application that enables students to develop their digital storytelling and speaking skills. According to this proposed research teacher feedback is received about the score of each mobile application from the teachers using them for a long time.

According to the teachers who used the mobile application, the most critical criterion for selecting a suitable mobile application is speed, because the speed of learning how to use the mobile application, integrating it with the language learning syllabus, and the materials retrieved from the application execution is typically the primary concern in the time bounded and simple language classroom of primary education. Teaching ability and accessibility are the second and third most weighted criteria, as they are pedagogically relevant. This means that the pedagogical dimension is critical to achieving suitable mobile applications and should not be overlooked.

The survey results allow us to conclude that the total scores of Kahoot, Toontastic, and Wordwall -are the three most top mobile applications that are found to be useful and pedagogically relevant within the group of both teachers and students. Specifically, toontastic 3D is found to be the most desirable and ranked mobile application.

Teachers who participated in this study are quite experienced in the mobile-assisted language learning methodology and provided their valuable feedback and ratings based on the present scenario of selecting appropriate mobile applications. Therefore, this research will support decision-makers in take proper and prudent mobile application selection decisions based on present situations. The ranking of mobile applications shows the current state of the prominent local and global mobile applications in terms of usefulness and joyfulness, which is expected to support decision-makers for future decision-making. The purpose of this study was to develop a selection framework for suitable mobile application selection in the language classroom of primary education which is one of Uzbekistan's most important educational sectors. The Analytical Hierarchy Process's weighting of the mobile application evaluation criteria indicates that innovating language teaching in primary education is in the lead position. The highest priority is given to the Toontastic, followed by Kahoot and Wordwall. Outcomes can be different for countries from different economic and social and pedagogical statuses, which is worth researching in the future. This study focuses only on the primary education sector. Other relevant sectors of language education such as higher education can be explored as well by utilizing the proposed mobile application selection framework.

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